

Figure S1.



Figure S2 Total sequences



OTU stats



Total OTUs by taxa



- Unassigned
- Other/unknown
- Opisthokonts-Other
- Opisthokont-Metazoa
- Opisthokont-Fungi
- Rhizaria-RAD (A,B,C)
- Rhizaria-Polycystines
- Rhizaria-Cercozoa
- Rhizaria-Acantharia
- Haptophytes
- Excavates
- Cryptophytes
- Archaeplastids-Other
- Archaeplastids-Chlorophytes
- Stramenopiles-Other
- Stramenopiles-Chrysophytes
- Stramenopiles-MAST
- Stramenopiles-Pelagophytes
- Stramenopiles-Diatoms
- Alveolates-Other
- Alveolates-Syndiniales
- Alveolates-Ciliates
- Alveolates-Dinoflagellates

